

THE EFFECTS OF DIRECTLY GROWN CARBON NANOSTRUCTURES ON THE WETTABILITY BETWEEN CF-EPOXY

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It is well known that CNT incorporated C-C composites shows enhanced mechanical properties like ILSS, IFSS. Even though, it is not studied how the directly grown CNT on CF can enhance these properties systematically. In this study, the effects of carbon nanostructures with different shapes on carbon fiber on the wettability with epoxy were investigated. Well aligned carbon nanostructures like CNT were directly grown on the carbon fiber matrix using simple thermal CVD method, results in two different shapes of carbon nanostructures such as vertical and/or loop like depending on the thermal process. In order to investigate the wettability properties, three different types of samples were prepared; S1: Carbon Fiber, S2: Vertical type CNT on CF, S3: Loop type CNT on CF and epoxy droplets introduced on these surfaces. Based on the SEM results, one can argue that directly grown carbon nanostructures on the CF can enhance the wettability with epoxy dramatically and which more dominantly depends on the shapes of grown carbon nanostructures, capillary effect, than surface chemical properties of carbon nanostructures.

Fig. 1. SEM results of three different types of grown carbon nanostructures on CF.

Fig.2 SEM results of three different types of samples wetted with epoxy.